

Abrupt termination of vitamin C from ICU patients may increase mortality: secondary analysis of the LOVIT trial

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Figure S1: Early part of the survival curves of the LOVIT trial

No. at Risk

Placebo	433	289	241
Vitamin C	429	267	226

The LOVIT trial [14] published the survival curves up to day 180. In this figure, the period of 4-day vitamin C supplementation is indicated by the black box.

On day 30, there were 289 patients alive in the placebo group, and 267 in the vitamin C group.

On day 180, there were 241 patients alive in the placebo group, and 226 in the vitamin C group [14].

Thus, between 30 and 180 days there were 48 deaths in the placebo group and 41 deaths in the vitamin C group. This gives RR = 0.93 (P = 0.7; 95% CI 0.63 – 1.35).

Thus, the period from 30 days to 180 days has such few deaths that the confidence interval is very wide.

Therefore the published 180-day survival curves do not provide relevant information beyond day 30.

However, extension of the survival curves up to day 180 causes that the 4-day period of vitamin C administration is packed to very short segment in the survival figure. This causes that it is very difficult for a reader of the LOVIT report [14] to notice that the harm in vitamin C group occurred *after* the termination of the 4-day vitamin C administration, and *not during* vitamin C as indicated by the authors: “those who received intravenous vitamin C had a higher risk of death or persistent organ dysfunction” [14].

14. Lamontagne et al. N Engl J Med. 2022;386:2387-2398. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmoa2200644>

Extraction of deaths from the survival curves over 11 days

The locations of the survival curve corners were measured with a graphics program and the locations were transformed to the number of deaths per day. The extraction was restricted to the 4-day vitamin C administration and 1 week thereafter since the question was to analyze if there was change in mortality by the abrupt termination of vitamin C administration. The left-hand side of this table shows the measurements in pixels and the calculated number of patients are on the right-hand side.

0 days	30 days	pixels per day			Vitamin C	Placebo			Total				
863	1287	14.13			N: 429	433			862				
	%	Pixels											
	100	128											
	0	1704											
Width of line	900	882	18										
Width of line	Half		9										
					Calculated				Rounded		Deaths per day		
	Vitamin C		Placebo		Alive	deaths	Alive	deaths			vitC	Placebo	Day
Day	Border	corrected	Border	corrected	Vitamin C	Δ/day	Placebo	Δ/day	Vitamin C	Placebo			
0		128		128	429.0		433.0		429.0	433.0			0
1	160	169	171	180	417.8	11.2	418.7	14.3	418.0	419.0	11	14	1
2	262	253	229	238	395.0	22.9	402.8	15.9	395.0	403.0	23	16	2
3	295	286	261	270	386.0	9.0	394.0	8.8	386.0	394.0	9	9	3
4	300	309	305	314	379.7	6.3	381.9	12.1	380.0	382.0	6	12	4
5	365	356	313	322	366.9	12.8	379.7	2.2	367.0	380.0	13	2	5
6	405	396	334	343	356.0	10.9	373.9	5.8	356.0	374.0	11	6	6
7	438	429	360	369	347.1	9.0	366.8	7.1	347.0	367.0	9	7	7
8	457	448	375	384	341.9	5.2	362.7	4.1	342.0	363.0	5	4	8
9	490	481	389	398	332.9	9.0	358.8	3.8	333.0	359.0	9	4	9
10	509	500	404	413	327.7	5.2	354.7	4.1	328.0	355.0	5	4	10
11	527	518	422	431	322.8	4.9	349.8	4.9	323.0	350.0	5	5	11
											Days 1-4	49	51
											Days 5-11	57	32
											Days 1-11	106	83

Printouts of statistical calculations

```
> table(LOVIT$day, LOVIT$dead, LOVIT$VitC)
, , = 0
```

	0	1
1	0	14
2	0	16
3	0	9
4	0	12
5	0	2
6	0	6
7	0	7
8	0	4
9	0	4
10	0	4
11	350	5

```
, , = 1
```

	0	1
1	0	11
2	0	23
3	0	9
4	0	6
5	0	13
6	0	11
7	0	9
8	0	5
9	0	9
10	0	5
11	323	5

```

> LOVIT_S <- Surv(LOVIT$day, LOVIT$dead)
>
> base <- coxph(LOVIT_S ~ LOVIT$VitC, method = "efron")

> summary(base)
Call:
coxph(formula = LOVIT_S ~ LOVIT$VitC, method = "efron")

n= 862, number of events= 189

              coef exp(coef) se(coef)      z Pr(>|z|)
LOVIT$VitC 0.276      1.318    0.147 1.88    0.06 .
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

              exp(coef) exp(-coef) lower .95 upper .95
LOVIT$VitC          1.32         0.759    0.989    1.76

Concordance= 0.533 (se = 0.018 )
Likelihood ratio test= 3.57 on 1 df,  p=0.06
Wald test              = 3.54 on 1 df,  p=0.06
Score (logrank) test = 3.56 on 1 df,  p=0.06

```

```

> days2 <- survSplit(Surv(LOVIT$day, LOVIT$dead) ~ ., cut=c(2.5),
  episode= "tgroup", data =LOVIT)
> days2b <- coxph(Surv(tstart, tstop, event) ~ VitC:strata(tgroup),
  data=days2, method = "efron")
>
> lrtest(base,days2b)
Likelihood ratio test

Model 1: LOVIT_S ~ LOVIT$VitC
Model 2: Surv(tstart, tstop, event) ~ VitC:strata(tgroup)
  #Df LogLik Df Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
1    1 -1253
2    2 -1253 1  0.48  0.49
>
> #####
>
> days3 <- survSplit(Surv(LOVIT$day, LOVIT$dead) ~ ., cut=c(3.5),
  episode= "tgroup", data =LOVIT)
> days3b <- coxph(Surv(tstart, tstop, event) ~ VitC:strata(tgroup),
  data=days3, method = "efron")
>
> lrtest(base,days3b)
Likelihood ratio test

Model 1: LOVIT_S ~ LOVIT$VitC
Model 2: Surv(tstart, tstop, event) ~ VitC:strata(tgroup)
  #Df LogLik Df Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
1    1 -1253
2    2 -1253 1    1  0.32
>
> #####
>
> days4 <- survSplit(Surv(LOVIT$day, LOVIT$dead) ~ ., cut=c(4.5),
  episode= "tgroup", data =LOVIT)
> days4b <- coxph(Surv(tstart, tstop, event) ~ VitC:strata(tgroup),
  data=days4, method = "efron")
>
> days4b
> summary(days4b)
Call:
coxph(formula = Surv(tstart, tstop, event) ~ VitC:strata(tgroup),
  data = days4, method = "efron")

n= 1624, number of events= 189

              coef exp(coef) se(coef)      z Pr(>|z|)
VitC:strata(tgroup)tgroup=1 -0.0282  0.9722  0.2000 -0.14  0.8878
VitC:strata(tgroup)tgroup=2  0.6302  1.8781  0.2209  2.85  0.0043 **
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

              exp(coef) exp(-coef) lower .95 upper .95
VitC:strata(tgroup)tgroup=1  0.972  1.029  0.657  1.44
VitC:strata(tgroup)tgroup=2  1.878  0.532  1.218  2.90

Concordance= 0.537 (se = 0.018 )
Likelihood ratio test= 8.52 on 2 df, p=0.01
Wald test = 8.16 on 2 df, p=0.02
Score (logrank) test = 8.43 on 2 df, p=0.01

```

```

> exp(confint(days4b))
                2.5 % 97.5 %
VitC:strata(tgroup) tgroup=1  0.66    1.4
VitC:strata(tgroup) tgroup=2  1.22    2.9
>
> lrtest(base, days4b)
Likelihood ratio test

Model 1: LOVIT_S ~ LOVIT$VitC
Model 2: Surv(tstart, tstop, event) ~ VitC:strata(tgroup)
  #Df LogLik Df Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
1    1  -1253
2    2  -1251  1  4.95    0.026 *
>
> #####
>
> days5 <- survSplit(Surv(LOVIT$day, LOVIT$dead) ~ ., cut=c(5.5),
  episode= "tgroup", data =LOVIT)
> days5b <- coxph(Surv(tstart, tstop, event) ~ VitC:strata(tgroup),
  data=days5, method = "efron")
>
> lrtest(base, days5b)
Likelihood ratio test

Model 1: LOVIT_S ~ LOVIT$VitC
Model 2: Surv(tstart, tstop, event) ~ VitC:strata(tgroup)
  #Df LogLik Df Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
1    1  -1253
2    2  -1253  1  0.82    0.36
>
> #####
>
> days6 <- survSplit(Surv(LOVIT$day, LOVIT$dead) ~ ., cut=c(6.5),
  episode= "tgroup", data =LOVIT)
> days6b <- coxph(Surv(tstart, tstop, event) ~ VitC:strata(tgroup),
  data=days6, method = "efron")
>
> lrtest(base, days6b)
Likelihood ratio test

Model 1: LOVIT_S ~ LOVIT$VitC
Model 2: Surv(tstart, tstop, event) ~ VitC:strata(tgroup)
  #Df LogLik Df Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
1    1  -1253
2    2  -1253  1  0.23    0.63
>

```

Days 5-7

```
> table(LOVIT7$day, LOVIT7$dead, LOVIT7$VitC)
, , = 0
```

	0	1
1	0	14
2	0	16
3	0	9
4	0	12
5	0	2
6	0	6
7	0	7
8	4	0
9	4	0
10	4	0
11	355	0

```
, , = 1
```

	0	1
1	0	11
2	0	23
3	0	9
4	0	6
5	0	13
6	0	11
7	0	9
8	5	0
9	9	0
10	5	0
11	328	0

```
> days4_7 <- survSplit(Surv(LOVIT7$day, LOVIT7$dead) ~ ., cut=c(4.5),
  episode= "tgroup", data =LOVIT7)
```

```
> days4b_7 <- coxph(Surv(tstart, tstop, event) ~ VitC:strata(tgroup),
  data=days4_7, method = "efron")
```

```
>
```

```
> summary(days4b_7)
```

```
Call:
```

```
coxph(formula = Surv(tstart, tstop, event) ~ VitC:strata(tgroup),
  data = days4_7, method = "efron")
```

```
n= 1624, number of events= 148
```

	coef	exp(coef)	se(coef)	z	Pr(> z)
VitC:strata(tgroup)tgroup=1	-0.0282	0.9722	0.2000	-0.14	0.8878
VitC:strata(tgroup)tgroup=2	0.8266	2.2856	0.3114	2.65	0.0079 **

```
---
```

```
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

	exp(coef)	exp(-coef)	lower .95	upper .95
VitC:strata(tgroup)tgroup=1	0.972	1.029	0.657	1.44
VitC:strata(tgroup)tgroup=2	2.286	0.438	1.241	4.21

Days 8-11

```
> days7 <- survSplit(Surv(LOVIT$day, LOVIT$dead) ~ ., cut=c(7.5),
  episode= "tgroup", data =LOVIT)
> days7b <- coxph(Surv(tstart, tstop, event) ~ VitC:strata(tgroup),
  data=days7, method = "efron")
>
> summary(days7b)
Call:
coxph(formula = Surv(tstart, tstop, event) ~ VitC:strata(tgroup),
  data = days7, method = "efron")
```

n= 1576, number of events= 189

	coef	exp(coef)	se(coef)	z	Pr(> z)
VitC:strata(tgroup)tgroup=1	0.237	1.268	0.165	1.44	0.15
VitC:strata(tgroup)tgroup=2	0.415	1.514	0.317	1.31	0.19

	exp(coef)	exp(-coef)	lower .95	upper .95
VitC:strata(tgroup)tgroup=1	1.27	0.789	0.917	1.75
VitC:strata(tgroup)tgroup=2	1.51	0.660	0.814	2.82

Days 30-180

```
riskratio(41, 48, 267, 289)
```

	Disease	Nondisease	Total
Exposed	41	226	267
Nonexposed	48	241	289

Risk ratio estimate and its significance probability

```
data: 41 48 267 289
```

```
p-value = 0.7
```

```
95 percent confidence interval:
```

```
0.631 1.355
```

```
sample estimates:
```

```
[1] 0.925
```